

FUNCTIONALLY GRADIENT COATING FOR C/Mg COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber for casting C/Mg composites with the UTS up to 700 MPa ($V_f=0.2$). The coating consisted of three layers: inside pyrocarbon layer, outside aluminum layer and intermediate gradient layer C/SiC/Si. This coating was fabricated by chemical vapor deposition and the C/Mg composite was performed by pressure-regulated infiltration. Many functions of the coating, such as wetting agent, diffusion and reaction barrier, releaser of residual thermal stresses and tailor of interfacial bonding strength, are also discussed.

Key words: metal matrix composites, fiber coating, chemical vapor deposition

1. INTRODUCTION

It is of great importance to control the structure and behaviour of the fiber/matrix interface during fabrication and service. Among the various methods to control the interface, one of the potential way is fiber coating. For carbon fiber-reinforced magnesium (C/Mg), silicon dioxide coating was probably the best coating [1]. However, this coating only has two functions: promoting wetting and preventing degradation of carbon fiber by magnesium. In fact, the silicon dioxide coating reacts with molten magnesium to form MgO, Mg₂SiO₄ and MgSiO₃, and these brittle reaction products are detrimental to the mechanical properties of C/Mg composites [2]. According to mechanical, physical and chemical coordination between fiber and matrix, the fiber coating should act as wetting agent, diffusion and reaction barrier, releaser of residual thermal stresses, tailor of interfacial shear strength, etc. Obviously, the previous coatings, whether they are single coatings or double coatings, are very difficult to meet the above requirements of the fiber coating. To solve this problem, a functionally gradient coating for C/Mg composites is presented and discussed in this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

PAN-based carbon fiber was used and each bundle had 1000 filaments. Some properties of the fiber are listed in Table 1. The functionally gradient coating for C/Mg composites was performed by chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the CVD apparatus, by which carbon fiber can be coated continuously. Two deposition chambers were used: one was a cold-wall reactor where carbon fibers were electrically heated and coated by pyrocarbon and C/SiC/Si gradient coatings, the other was a hot-wall reactor where carbon fibers were coated by aluminum. SiCl₄, Al(CH₃)₃, C₄H₁₀, H₂ and Ar were used as source materials, and the possible

chemical reactions are as follows [3]:

Table 1. Properties of carbon fiber*.

UTS (MPa)	E (GPa)	Elongation (%)	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (μm)
2500-3500	220-230	1.30-1.80	1.76	6-8

* UTS—Ultimate tensile strength.

E—Elastic modulus.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the CVD apparatus for functionally gradient coating.

The functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber was obtained by controlling the temperature field and vapor concentration field in deposition chamber.

The magnesium matrix used was Mg-7.5~9.0% Al-0.2~0.8% Zn alloy. Using coated fibers, C/Mg composite was fabricated by pressure-regulated infiltration. The infiltration process is a single step process for C/Mg composites, and the fabrication parameters, such as fiber temperature, melt temperature, pressure and infiltration rate, can be controlled simultaneously. The specimens dimensions were 100mm long and 6mm in diameter.

Coated fibers were characterized by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) and scanning Auger multiprobe (SAM). Tensile tests were performed on an Instron 1196 tensile machine at an actuator velocity of 0.5mm/sec.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model of a functionally gradient coating for C/Mg composites is shown in Figure 2. In gener-

Figure 2. Model of functionally gradient coating for C/Mg composites.

Figure 3. Transversal composition profile of the coated fiber by SAM.

Figure 4. Morphology of functionally gradient coating on carbon fiber.

Figure 5. Micrograph of coated carbon fiber.

Figure 6. Micrograph of coated 2-D fabric.

Figure 7. Micrograph of C/Mg composite.

al, the coating consisted of three layers. Its inside layer near carbon fiber is pyrocarbon and its outside layer is pure aluminum. the intermediate layer between pyrocarbon and aluminum, namely gradient layer, consisted of three sublayers: C/SiC sublayer, SiC sublayer and SiC/Si sublayer. Here, the chemical composition of C/SiC sublayer changes gradually from pyrocarbon to silicon carbide and SiC/Si sublayer from silicon carbide to silicon.

Figure 3 shows the transversal composition profile of the coated carbon fiber by SAM, and it confirms that the chemical composition of the coating for C/Mg composite is keeping with above model. As shown in Figure 4, the average thickness of the coating is about 0.5 μ m. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show that each fiber or 2-D fabric is uniformly and continuously coated. The tensile properties of coated fibers also indicated that the fibers were slightly damaged during fabrication.

Figure 7 shows that the coated carbon fibers distribute uniformly in magnesium matrix. Table 2 gives a comparison of longitudinal tensile strengths for C/Mg composite with different coatings at room temperature. As can be seen, fiber coating has a drastic effect on the longitudinal tensile strength. The measured strength declines from 88% of ROM for C/Mg composite with functionally gradient coating to about 43% of ROM for C/Mg composite with single coating such as SiO₂, Si or SiC. This reduction in the composite strength is strongly related to the functions of the coatings during fabrication and service.

Table 2. Longitudinal tensile strength of C/Mg composite at room temperature.

Fiber coating	Vol. % fiber	Coating thickness (μ m)	UTS (MPa)	ROM** (MPa)	UTS/ROM (%)
SiO ₂ *	20	0.1	354	808	43.8
Si	20	0.1	343	808	42.5
SiC	20	0.2	338	808	41.8
SiC+Si	20	0.4	425	808	52.6
C/SiC/Si***	15	0.5	410	671	61.1
	20	0.5	528	808	65.3
C/SiC/Si/Al***	15	0.5	581	671	86.6
	20	0.5	712	808	88.1

* SiO₂ coating was performed by Sol-Gel method, and the other coatings by CVD.

** ROM—Rule of mixtures.

*** These coatings are functionally gradient coatings.

The various coatings listed in Table 2, whether they are single coatings or double coatings even functionally gradient coatings, have a basic function: promoting wetting. However, their wetting mechanisms are different, and thus have different effect on interfacial properties. For silicon dioxide coating, wetting is achieved by a reaction between the molten magnesium and the silicon dioxide coating to form magnesium oxide and magnesium silicate [1]. For silicon carbide coating, wetting is also achieved by a reaction between the molten magnesium and the silicon carbide coat-

ing, but to form Mg_2Si [4]. For silicon coating (including other coatings in which outside layer is silicon), diffusion of silicon towards the molten magnesium forms Mg_2Si to achieve wetting. The formation of these brittle products at the fiber-matrix interface is detrimental to composite strength, and this is one of the reasons why the strengths of C/Mg composite with these coatings are generally lower than that with functionally gradient coating C/SiC/Si/Al (see Table 2). In addition, the poor tensile properties of C/Mg composite with silicon carbide coating are also attributed to poor wetting between silicon carbide and molten matrix. Aluminum is one of the alloying elements in some magnesium alloy (such as AZ91) and can be wetted easily by molten magnesium. For functionally gradient coating C/SiC/Si/Al, wetting is achieved by mutual dissolution between aluminum layer and molten matrix, and no detrimental products can be found at interface. The suitable thickness of aluminum layer is directly related to the processing parameters of pressure-regulated infiltration. In order to prevent aluminum layer from exhausting before completed solidification of molten matrix, the minimum thickness of aluminum layer is approximately $0.1\mu m$.

Aluminum or silicon coating poorly protects the carbon fibers against chemical degradation during fabrication and service. Among the various coatings proposed, silicon carbide is one of the most efficient protective coatings due to its chemical stability at high temperatures. However, there is a big mismatch between the coefficient of temperature expansion (CTE) of silicon carbide and that of carbon fiber. This difference of CTE will cause residual thermal stresses at the interface during fabrication as well as during service, and consequently lead to deteriorate the interfacial properties. The poor tensile strengths of C/Mg composites with single coating (such as silicon dioxide or silicon) or double coating (such as silicon carbide plus silicon) are also attributed to above two reasons (poor protection of fiber and a big mismatch of CTE). To solve this problem, a gradient layer is coated on carbon fiber. The gradient layer equals innumerable intermediate layers for matching the difference of CTE, and this layer can be fabricated conveniently and economically by CVD. The suitable thickness of gradient layer can be calculated by following equation [5]

$$C_1 \{F(a/(a+C_1))\}^2 = G_c^* / \pi \varepsilon_{f0}^2 E_f \tag{5}$$

where a is the radius of the fiber, G_c^* is the strain energy release rate of the fiber, ε_{f0} is the fracture strain of the fiber without brittle layer, E_f is the elastic modulus of the fiber and $F(a/(a+C_1))$ is the geometry correction factor related to relative thickness of fiber and brittle layer. Silicon carbide and silicon are brittle materials and the thickness of gradient layer should be below the C_1 in order to protect the fibers. For the carbon-fiber used in this study, the calculated value of C_1 is $0.25\mu m$.

Excellent tensile properties of C/Mg composite with functionally gradient coating are also attributed to a soft pyrocarbon between carbon fiber and gradient layer. If the notches forms in the matrix and extend into fiber easily, the composite will fracture at low stress, and if the crack tip develops easily along the interface, the transversal strength will not be high. Besides, it has been shown that the crack tip stresses are very sensitive to the modulus ratio [6], and the tensile stress parallel to the interface increases considerably as the modulus of the cracked phase decrease. Therefore, the soft pyrocarbon layer should be coated on carbon fiber to adjust the interfacial strength. This layer is beneficial to the longitudinal strength of composites but not to the transverse strength if it is too thick. The optimum longitudinal and transverse strengths can be obtained if the following equation exists [7]:

$$\sigma_f > \sigma_f^* > \sigma_f^\Delta > \sigma_f^* \tag{6}$$

where σ_t is the strength of uncoated fiber, σ_t^o is the fiber stress at which a notch is formed on coated fiber, σ_t^* is the fiber stress at which the notch extends into fiber and σ_t^Δ is the debonding strength of coated fiber. Here, the σ_t^Δ can be adjusted by changing the thickness of pyrocarbon layer. According to equation 6, the suitable thickness for C/Mg composites is 0.1~0.15 μm .

4. CONCLUSIONS

A functionally gradient coating C/SiC/Si/Al on carbon fiber for C/Mg composites was fabricated and analysed. The conclusions are as follows.

(1) The functionally gradient coating has many functions, including wetting agent, diffusion and reaction barrier, releaser of residual thermal stresses, tailor of interfacial shear strength, etc. This coating can solve nearly all the problems of the interface during fabrication and service.

(2) The coating can be fabricated conveniently and economically by chemical vapor deposition. The structure and properties of coated fibers also prove that CVD is a successful method for this coating.

(3) Using coated fibers, C/Mg composite with the UTS up to 700 MPa ($V_f=0.2$) was successfully fabricated by pressure-regulated infiltration.

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